

PAROBOLIK TIPDAGI TENGLAMARNING KO'P KOMPLEMENTALI MUHITDA FILTIRATSIYA JARAYONLARINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA SONLI YECHISH

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Parabolik tipdagi nohiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi uchun qo'yilgan Koshi masalasini ko'rib chiqamiz

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left| \frac{\partial u^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{du^{m_1}}{dx} \right) \pm cv_1(t) \frac{\partial y}{\partial x} - b_1 u^{q_1} \left| \frac{\partial v^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_1} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\left| \frac{\partial v^{m_2}}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} \frac{dv^{m_2}}{dx} \right) \pm cv_1(t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - b_1 v^{q_2} \left| \frac{\partial u^{m_2}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$u(x, 0) = u_0(x) \geq 0 \quad v(x, 0) = v_0(x) \geq 0 \quad x \in R \quad (2)$$

bu yerda $m_i \geq 1$, $p_i > 1 + 1/m$, $q_i > 0$, $p_i > 0$ ($i=1,2$), $p > 0$ - muhitning sonli parametrlari, $u_0(x)$ va $v_0(x)$ musbat aniqlangan uzluksiz tashuvchili funksiyalar (muhit temperaturasi).

(1), (2) chegaraviy masala chiziqsiz muhitda diffuziya jarayonini matematik modellashtirishda, g'ovak muhitlardagi suyuqliklar oqimi, biologik populyatsiya dinamikasi, politropik filtratsiya, sinergetika masalalarini va boshqa qator sohalardagi masalalarni yechishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Masalan $u(x, t)$ va $v(x, t)$ lar ikki biologik populyatsiyaning zichligini yoki issiqlik tarqalish jarayonida ikki g'ovak muhitlarning haroratini ifodalaydi.

Sonli yechish. Buning uchun fazoviy koordinata bo'yicha

$$S_h = \{x_i = i \cdot h, h > 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, n \cdot h = b\}$$

va vaqt bo'yicha

$$V_h = \{x_i = i \cdot h, h > 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n, n \cdot h = b\}$$

to'r qurib olamiz.

(1) tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(B_1(u) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + cv_1(t) \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - b_1 u^{q_1} \left| \frac{\partial v^{m_1}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_1} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(B_2(v) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + cv_2(t) \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - b_2 v^{q_2} \left| \frac{\partial u^{m_2}}{\partial x} \right|^{p_2} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$B_1(u) = m_1 \left| k_1 u^{k_1-1} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} u^{m_1-1}$$

$$B_2(v) = m_2 \left| k_2 v^{k_2-1} \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right|^{p-2} v^{m_2-1}$$

va quyidagi boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar bilan sonli yechish sxemasini quramiz.

$$\begin{cases} u(t, 0) = \phi_1(t) > 0, \quad u(t, b) = \phi_2(t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T] \\ v(t, b) = \phi_3(t) = 0, \quad v(t, 0) = \phi_4(t) = 0, \quad t \in [0, T] \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), \quad v(x, 0) = v_0(x), \quad x \in R_+ \end{cases}$$

Balans usulini qoʻllagan holda (20), (2) masalani oshkormas ayirmali sxema bilan almashtiramiz va ayirmali masalaga ega boʻlamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1}(y)(y_{i+1}^{j+1} - y_i^{j+1}) - a_i(y)(y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1})) + c_1 v_1(t) \frac{y_i^{j+1} - y_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h} - G_1(y_i^j, g_i^j) \\ \frac{g_i^{j+1} - g_i^j}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} (a_{i+1}(g)(g_{i+1}^{j+1} - g_i^{j+1}) - a_i(g)(g_i^{j+1} - g_{i-1}^{j+1})) + c_2 v_2(t) \frac{g_i^{j+1} - g_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h} - G_2(y_i^j, g_i^j) \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$G_1(y_i^j, g_i^j) = b_1(y_i^j)^{q_1} \left| m_1(g_i^j)^{m_1-1} \frac{g_i^j - g_{i-1}^j}{h} \right|^{p_1}$$

$$G_2(y_i^j, g_i^j) = b_1(g_i^j)^{q_2} \left| m_2(y_i^j)^{m_2-1} \frac{y_i^j - y_{i-1}^j}{h} \right|^{p_2}$$

Bu yerda $a(y)$ va $a(g)$ larni hisoblash uchun quyidagi formulalardan biri qoʻllaniladi

$$\begin{cases} a_i(y) = B_1 \left(\frac{y_i^j - y_{i-1}^j}{2} \right) \\ a_i(g) = B_2 \left(\frac{g_i^j - g_{i-1}^j}{2} \right) \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{cases} a_i(y) = \frac{B_1(y_i^j) + B_1(y_{i-1}^j)}{2} \\ a_i(g) = \frac{B_2(g_i^j) + B_2(g_{i-1}^j)}{2} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

(21) tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun oddiy iteratsiya usulidan foydalanamiz va quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left(a_{i+1}^s(y) \left(y_{i+1}^{s+1} - y_i^{s+1} \right) - a_i^s(y) \left(y_i^{s+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1} \right) \right) + c_1 v_1(t) \frac{y_i^{s+1} - y_{i-1}^{s+1}}{h} - G_1 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right) \\ \frac{g_i^{s+1} - g_i^s}{\tau} = \frac{1}{h^2} \left(a_{i+1}^s(g) \left(g_{i+1}^{s+1} - g_i^{s+1} \right) - a_i^s(g) \left(g_i^{s+1} - g_{i-1}^{s+1} \right) \right) + c_2 v_2(t) \frac{g_i^{s+1} - g_{i-1}^{s+1}}{h} - G_2 \left(y_i^s, g_i^s \right) \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

bunda $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

y_i^{s+1} va g_i^{s+1} ga nisbatan (24) ayirmali sxemalar chiziqi. y va g ning qiymati, y_i^s, g_i^s uchun

boshlangʻich iteratsiya sifatida vaqt boʻyicha avvalgi qadamdan olinadi: $y_i^{0+1} = y_i^0, g_i^{0+1} = g_i^0$.

Iteratsion sxema boʻyicha hisoblashda iteratsiya aniqligi beriladi va jarayon quyidagi shartlar qanoatlantirilguncha davom etadi

$$\max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| y_i^{s+1} - y_i^s \right| < \varepsilon, \max_{0 \leq i \leq n} \left| g_i^{s+1} - g_i^s \right| < \varepsilon$$

(24) ayirmali tenglamalar sistemasiga quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$A_i = \frac{\tau}{h^2} a_{i+1} \left(y \right) y_{i+1}^{s+1}$$

$$B_{1i} = \left(\frac{\tau}{h^2} a_i \binom{s}{y} - \frac{\tau c}{h} \nu(t_j) \right) y_{i+1}^{s+1}$$

$$A_{2i} = \frac{\tau}{h^2} a_{i+1} \binom{s}{g} g_{i+1}^{s+1}$$

$$B_{2i} = \left(\frac{\tau}{h^2} a_i \binom{s}{g} - \frac{\tau c}{h} \nu(t_j) \right) g_{i+1}^{s+1}$$

$$C_{1i} = A_{1i} + B_{1i} + 1$$

$$C_{2i} = A_{2i} + B_{2i} + 1$$

$$F_{1i} = y_i^j - \tau G_1 \left(y_i^j, g_i^j \right)$$

$$F_{2i} = g_i^j - \tau G_2 \left(y_i^j, g_i^j \right)$$

Natijada (24) sistema quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\begin{cases} A_{1i} y_{i+1}^{j+1} - C_{1i} y_i^{j+1} + B_{1i} y_{i-1}^{j+1} = -F_{1i}, & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1 \\ A_{2i} g_{i+1}^{j+1} - C_{2i} g_i^{j+1} + B_{2i} g_{i-1}^{j+1} = -F_{2i}, & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

(25) algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi yechish uchun haydash (progonka) usulini qo'llaymiz.

Ushbu metodga asosan

$$\begin{cases} \bar{y}_i = \alpha_{1i} (\beta_{1i} + \bar{y}_{i+1}), \\ \bar{g}_i = \alpha_{2i} (\beta_{2i} + \bar{g}_{i+1}), \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

bu yerda $\alpha_{1i}, \alpha_{2i}, \beta_{1i}, \beta_{2i}$ - koeffitsientlar quyidagicha hisoblanadi:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{1i+1} = \frac{B_{1i}}{C_{1i} - \alpha_{1i} A_{1i}}, \\ \alpha_{2i+1} = \frac{B_{2i}}{C_{2i} - \alpha_{2i} A_{2i}}, \\ \beta_{1i+1} = \frac{A_{1i} \beta_{1i} + F_{1i}}{C_{1i} - \alpha_{1i} A_{1i}}, \\ \beta_{2i+1} = \frac{A_{2i} \beta_{2i} + F_{2i}}{C_{2i} - \alpha_{2i} A_{2i}}, \end{cases}$$

bunda $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Boshlang'ich $\alpha_{10}, \alpha_{20}, \beta_{10}, \beta_{20}$ qiymatlar yuqorida berilgan chegaraviy shartlardan topiladi.

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